

Zichiji 資持記

also known as “Sifenlu shanfan buque xingshichao zichiji 四分律刪繁補闕行事鈔資持記”

By xingyi wang, Harvard University

Entry tags: Vinaya commentary, Dharmaguptaka Vinaya, Vinaya school, Religious Group, Text, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

This entry aims to document Zichiji, a commentary of Dharmaguptaka Vinaya (Buddhist monastic rules) written by Yuanzhao (1048-1116). Zichiji is a secondary commentary based on a root commentary of Daoxuan's (596-667) Sifenlü shanfan buque xingshichao (Xingshichao). Divided into 16 volumes, it is a complete commentary of Daoxuan's original work, which is based on the Dharmaguptaka Vinaya. Like Xingshichao, Zichiji refers to various Vinaya-related texts and Buddhist materials and is intended to be used as a comprehensive guide to the Buddhist monastic way of living. Zichiji covers a wide range of monastic practices and management, such as ordination ritual, repentance ritual, funerary practices, daily management of the monastery, and the relationships with laypersons. Unlike Xingshichao, it includes valuable information on the Song Buddhist monasticism and Yuanzhao's debate with other Vinaya masters in his time. In terms of the transmission history of the text, multiple historical sources record that Zichiji was canonized during the Southern Song period. However, we do not have a material copy of any Buddhist canon which contains this text. The current canonization of the Zichiji can only be traced to the modern compilation of Zokuzōkyō in 1902. The popularity of Zichiji is a symbolic mark for the beginning of an institutionalized Vinaya school in China. A litter earlier than Zichiji, Yunkan's Huizhengji (not extant) was a parallel work circulated in the Northern Song. Yuanzhao and Yunkan demonstrated different interpretations of Daoxuan and the Vinaya. After the Yuan Dynasty, Zichiji, together with other commentaries written by Yuanzhao, did not survive in the continent. It has been preserved in multiple monastic libraries and archives in Japan, such as Otani University library, Seikado Bunko Library, and Kanazawa Library, and brought back to China in the modern period. The preservation of Zichiji bespeaks active Buddhist communication and exchange on the Vinaya between China, Korea, and Japan in the medieval period during the 12th-14th centuries. Exchange among different countries became possible together with the reopening of the maritime trade route interrupted by the end of the Tang and the period of Five Dynasties and Ten Kingdoms. Zichiji was studied in Japan as one of the foundational commentaries for the Vinaya and thus facilitated the Vinaya revival movement in Kamakura Japan. Yuanzhao, as the author of Zichiji, was commemorated as one of the patriarchs of the Vinaya school. In the modern period, Chinese Vinaya master Hongyi wrote an annotated version of Zichiji, and it has been further edited and published in China.

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1085 CE

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

Region tags: Asia, East Asia

Northern Song

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Daoxuan, Yuanzhao, Hongyi, and Xuecheng. *Si Fen Lü Xing Shi Chao Zi Chi Ji Jiao Shi*. 第1版. ed. Nan Shan Lü Dian Jiao Shi Xi Lie ; 6. Beijing: Zong Jiao Wen Hua Chu Ban She, 2015.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

– Source 1: Asada, Masahiro. *Kairitsu O Shiru Tame No Shōjiten*. 初版. ed. Ryūkoku Daigaku Bukkyō Bunka Kenkyū Sōsho ; 31. Kyōto-shi: Ryūkoku Daigaku Bukkyō Bunka Kenkyūjo, 2014.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

– Source 1: Genryu Yamamoto, A Critique of the Zen Sect based on an Examination of the "Sifenlu Xingshichao Zichiji (『四分律行事鈔資持記』), in JOURNAL OF SŌTŌ STUDIES (SHŪGAKU KENKYŪ), 2006(48), p. 205-210

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

– Source 1: Ippei Okamoto, The Huizheng-jia and Zichi-jia in the Vinaya school during the Northern Song Period, Annual report of the Zen Institute, 1999 (10), p. 63-77.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

– Source 1: Xingyi Wang, Dharma in Common: Yuanzhao and the Resurgence of Buddhist Monasticism in Medieval East Asia. Dissertation. Harvard University, 2021.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL:

<http://buddhaspace.org/dict/fk/data/%25E8%25B3%2587%25E6%258C%2581%25E8%25A8%2598.html>

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://cbetaonline.dila.edu.tw/zh/T1805>

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

— Yes

Notes: Zichiji was canonized in the Shinsan dainihon zokuzōkyō 新纂大日本統藏經. Tōkyō: Kokusho kankōkai. 1975-1989.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Tomb

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Cemetery

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Temple

— Yes

Notes: The original printed copy of Zichiji is preserved in several Japanese Buddhist monasteries, such as Kosanji, Toji, Todaiji, Sennyuji, and Toshodaiji. Kanazawa bunko also has a collection of Zichiji

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Shrine

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Altar

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Devotional marker

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Cenotaph

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Church

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Mosque

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Synagogue

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Triumphal Arch**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Monument**

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Mass Gathering Point**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Cave(s)**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Hilltops**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Other natural sanctuaries**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Boundary markers or lines**

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Domestic contexts**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Library/archive**

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Methods of Composition

— Printed with moveable type

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Number of sheets**

— Bound

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

— Paper

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Specify type of paper**

–Specify: 13th century woodblock print paper made in the Southern Song

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Yes

Notes: The text might have ritualistic use together with the portrait of Yuanzhao and Daoxuan in specific gatherings in the monasteries.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Alpha-numeric symbolism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Use of geometric/abstract designs?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Floral or other natural imagery?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: This text has been printed in the Southern Song and transmitted to Japan in multiple copies.

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Printed with moveable type

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Number of sheets

– Bound

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

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Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

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↳ Tomb

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Cemetery

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

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↳ Devotional marker

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Church

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

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Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Synagogue

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Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

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↳ **Mass Gathering Point**

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Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

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↳ **Cave(s)**

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Hilltops**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ **Other natural sanctuaries**

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Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
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↳ Boundary markers or lines

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
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↳ Domestic contexts

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Region: Northern Song

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Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

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Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

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Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Alpha-numeric symbolism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Use of geometric/abstract designs?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Floral or other natural imagery?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The composition of the work is not sponsored by the imperial court, however, in the 12th century, it gained authority by receiving the endorsement from the emperor Song Lizong (1205-1264)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Notes: One effective way of missionary work related the Vinaya school was the conferral of the bodhisattva precepts for both monastics and commoners. Eison's 叡尊 religious group is the most well-

known in this practice.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: Missionary work is encouraged but not a necessity.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

— Field doesn't know

Notes: This text contains monastic rituals that can be used in the context of Buddhist monasteries.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

— No

Notes: As a sub-commentary of Daoxuan's original Xingshichao, it is considered one of the two most popular and authoritative commentaries produced in the Northern Song. The other one is Yunkan's 允堪 Sifenlu xingshichao huizhengji 四分律行事鈔會正記, which did not survive.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

— Yes

Notes: Since this is already a sub-commentary, there is no further commentary on this work. However, later Vinaya master did compose interpretative essays to summarize the essential part of Zichiji, such as Shouyi 守一 and Miaolian's 妙蓮 works.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

— Yes

Notes: The other popular sub-commentary was Yunkan's Huizhengji, which indicated that in the Northern Song, Zichiji was not the only authoritative interpretation of Daoxuan's Xingshichao. As Yuanzhao illustrated in his writing, there are several other commentarial traditions that coexisted in the Northern Song. However, other sub-commentaries of Xingshichao did not acquire the form of an institutional organization recognized as Nanshan Vinaya School.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

— No

Notes: As a scholastic monastic commentarial tradition, the influence of the government is manifested in the qualification of receiving the ordination but not in terms of interpreting the text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

— Yes

Notes: Yuanzhao's disciples Shouyi 守一 and Miaolian 妙蓮 have different interpretations of main topics of Zichiji.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

— Yes

Notes: For the highly technical language of the commentary, it is assumed that only a small number of specially trained Vinaya masters had full access to the text and can preach the content.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

— No

Notes: The majority of Vinaya masters in this tradition are male, but it does not mean female monastics are completely excluded from the tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

— Yes

Notes: Qualified Vinaya masters should be fully ordained Buddhist monastics and should hold good monastic record for over ten years.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

— Yes

Notes: Canonized in modern time Shinsan dainihon zokuzōkyō 新纂大日本統藏經. Tōkyō: Kokusho kankōkai. 1975-1989. But in the premodern period, the text has been constantly reprinted and studied.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

— Yes

Notes: Written in classic Chinese, with passages cited from original Vinaya texts and commentaries translated into Chinese.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Archaic ritual language?

— Yes

Notes: there are ritual processes that are quoted from translated Chinese texts from Sanskrit.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

— No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

— Institutions

Notes: the original Vinaya texts are considered authoritative by Buddhist communities.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

— Yes

Notes: Zichiji is one of the central texts for the Vinaya and precepts revival movement in the Song China and Kamakura period of Japan.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

— Yes

Notes: Zichiji contains monastic rituals covering all aspects of Buddhist monastic life, such as the ordination ritual, repentance ritual, annual summer retreat, and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it orally recited?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ On the reciter?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it read?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

— Specify: orination ritual, repentance ritual, funeral ritual and etc.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 20

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 2

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: bimonth repentance ritual regularly for monastics

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

Notes: As for the material significance of the text, Zichiji has been copied and transmitted in woodblock prints. The printing notes inserted in Zichiji indicated wide patronage of commoners and monastic for the printing career. The printing copies were carried back to Japan multiple times and only preserved in Japan after the Southern Song. In the Vinaya tradition, objects are particularly important. Chapters 30 to 35 of Zichiji focus on various objects used in Buddhist monasteries. The monastic robe is arguably the most important object for monastics. Yuanzhao also wrote a short piece for the objects possessed by monastics, called Fozhi biqu liuqutu 佛製比丘六物圖。

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it hidden?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can it be touched?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

— Yes

Notes: It contains passages about how to cleanse a ritual space by setting ritual boundaries. Also in Buddhism, the repentance ritual is considered an important practice for cleansing one's karmic sins.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Specify

— Specify: the text has been reprinted in Edo period and thus cannonized in modern time

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The composition of the work is not sponsored by the imperial court, however, in the 12th century, it gained authority by receiving the endorsement from the emperor Song Lizong (1205-1264)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This text contains monastic rituals that can be used in the context of Buddhist monasteries.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

Notes: As a sub-commentary of Daoxuan's original Xingshichao, it is considered one of the two most popular and authoritative commentaries produced in the Northern Song. The other one is Yunkan's 允堪 Sifenlu xingshichao huizhengji 四分律行事鈔會正記, which did not survive.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Since this is already a sub-commentary, there is no further commentary on this work. However, later Vinaya master did compose interpretative essays to summarize the essential part of Zichiji, such as Shouyi 守一 and Miaolian's 妙蓮 works.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

Notes: The other popular sub-commentary was Yunkan's Huizhengji, which indicated that in the Northern Song, Zichiji was not the only authoritative interpretation of Daoxuan's Xingshichao. As Yuanzhao illustrated in his writing, there are several other commentarial traditions that coexisted in the Northern Song. However, other sub-commentaries of Xingshichao did not acquire the form of an institutional organization recognized as Nanshan Vinaya School.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

Notes: As a scholastic monastic commentarial tradition, the influence of the government is manifested in the qualification of receiving the ordination but not in terms of interpreting the text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Yes

Notes: Yuanzhao's disciples Shouyi 守一 and Miaolian 妙蓮 have different interpretations of main topics of Zichiji.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: For the highly technical language of the commentary, it is assumed that only a small number of specially trained Vinaya masters had full access to the text and can preach the content.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

Notes: The majority of Vinaya masters in this tradition are male, but it does not mean female monastics are completely excluded from the tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– Yes

Notes: Qualified Vinaya masters should be fully ordained Buddhist monastics and should hold good monastic record for over ten years.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Canonized in modern time Shinsan dainihon zokuzōkyō 新纂大日本統藏經. Tōkyō: Kokusho kankōkai. 1975-1989. But in the premodern period, the text has been constantly reprinted and studied.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Notes: Written in classic Chinese, with passages cited from original Vinaya texts and commentaries translated into Chinese.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: there are ritual processes that are quoted from translated Chinese texts from Sanskrit.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

Notes: the original Vinaya texts are considered authoritative by Buddhist communities.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Notes: One effective way of missionary work related the Vinaya school was the conferral of the bodhisattva precepts for both monastics and commoners. Eison's 叡尊 religious group is the most well-known in this practice.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: Missionary work is encouraged but not a necessity.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Zichiji is one of the central texts for the Vinaya and precepts revival movement in the Song China and Kamakura period of Japan.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: Zichiji contains monastic rituals covering all aspects of Buddhist monastic life, such as the ordination ritual, repentance ritual, annual summer retreat, and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ On the reciter?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: orination ritual, repentance ritual, funeral ritual and etc.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 20

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 2

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: bimonth repentance ritual regularly for monastics

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

Notes: As for the material significance of the text, Zichiji has been copied and transmitted in woodblock prints. The printing notes inserted in Zichiji indicated wide patronage of commoners and monastic for the printing career. The printing copies were carried back to Japan multiple times and only preserved in Japan after the Southern Song. In the Vinaya tradition, objects are particularly important. Chapters 30 to 35 of Zichiji focus on various objects used in Buddhist monasteries. The monastic robe is arguably the most important object for monastics. Yuanzhao also wrote a short piece for the objects possessed by monastics, called Fozhi biqiu liuqutu 佛製比丘六物圖。

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– Yes

Notes: It contains passages about how to cleanse a ritual space by setting ritual boundaries. Also in Buddhism, the repentance ritual is considered an important practice for cleansing one's karmic sins.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Specify

–Specify: the text has been reprinted in Edo period and thus cannonized in modern time

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Nanshan Vinaya school is established based on the commentarial tradition founded by Daoxuan in the Tang and was institutionalized in the Song.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: the belief in the afterlife conforms to the typical Buddhist notion of six paths of existence and the possibility of gaining rebirth in another Buddha land

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: in the form of beings in the six paths, or rebirth in another Buddha land.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Notes: The conventional information is about the specific situation in China and in the Song and the moral aspect is attributed to the original Vinaya texts.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

— Only specialized religious class

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is an eschatology present in the text?

— Yes

Notes: The afterlife belief in Zichiji is combined with Amitabha's Pure Land belief in Yuanzhao's writing. As Pure Land belief was pervasive in Yuanzhao's time, particularly in the final dharma period, Zichiji intentionally emphasizes the importance of seeking rebirth in the Pure Land.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ At specified time in future

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ At unspecified time in near future

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ At some other time [specify]

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Divine judgment event

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Restoration of the world

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Establishment of new political system

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Establishment of new religious system

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other form of eschatology?

— Specify: none

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The commentary provides an authoritative interpretation of the Vinaya prescription.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In human form?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In animal/plant form?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

— Yes

Notes: Zichiji is one of the three sub-commentaries for Daoxuan's original commentaries. The other two are titled Sifenlü hanzhu jiebenshu xingzongji 四分律含注戒本疏行宗記. X39, no. 0714 and Sifenlü shanbu suiiji jiemo shu jiyuanji 四分律刪補隨機羯磨疏濟緣記. X41, no. 0728.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is there a sense of canonization?

— Yes

Notes: Canonization was recorded to be permitted by the Southern Song Emperor Lizong. However, there is no canonized text found in all extant Buddhist canon. The known canonization took place in the modern period.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

How is the authority established?

— Yes

Notes: the authority of Zichiji has two sources, one is that it is a sub-commentary of Xingshichao, the foundational commentary of the Vinaya; the second is from the Vinaya texts it comments on.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Can the canon be altered or added to?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the

larger canon?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done only by high god

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Generosity/charity

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Cooperation

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Moderation/frugality

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Beauty/attractiveness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Other important virtues

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Cremation?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Mummification?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Interment?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Cannibalism?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Feeding to animals?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Secondary burial?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: commentary traditon of the Buddhist Vinaya

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Notes: The calendar is arranged in a lunar calendar.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

Notes: all monastic activities such as ordination, repentance, summer retreat are prescribed a specific time in Zichiji.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Planting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Harvest?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Marriage?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Divorce?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Funerary services?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Trade/commerce?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: once a year

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?
– All members

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?
– number: 10

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Pilgrimages?
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Feasting?
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

For the worship of a deified human?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

For the worship of a deceased hero?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ A supreme high-god is present

— Yes

Notes: Many rituals such as the ordination ritual contain parts of inviting Buddhas and bodhisattvas to descend as witnesses.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: perfect virtue, wisdom

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Can reward
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Can punish
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can be hurt?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: make prophet, make monastic rules

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In trance possession

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Buddha, bodhisattva, and local gods are present invited to witness the ritual as if they are present. Buddhist statues and images are required to be treated as if they are Buddha and bodhisattva.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: control weather, hell

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

–Specify: heavenly beings and local deities might be included

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there orthopraxy checks?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there material offerings present?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

By the community?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ By specific individuals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

Other?

– Specify: setting boundaries and purification of the ritual space

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Zichiji is one of the three sub-commentaries for Daoxuan's original commentaries. The other two are titled Sifenlü hanzhu jiebenshu xingzongji 四分律含注戒本疏行宗記. X39, no. 0714 and Sifenlü shanbu sui ji jiemo shu jiyuanji 四分律刪補隨機羯磨疏濟緣記. X41, no. 0728.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Notes: Canonization was recorded to be permitted by the Southern Song Emperor Lizong. However, there is no canonized text found in all extant Buddhist canon. The known canonization took place in the modern period.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: the authority of Zichiji has two sources, one is that it is a sub-commentary of Xingshichao, the foundational commentary of the Vinaya; the second is from the Vinaya texts it comments on.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: commentary traditon of the Buddhist Vinaya

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Nanshan Vinaya school is established based on the commentarial tradition founded by Daoxuan in the Tang and was institutionalized in the Song.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The commentary provides an authoritative interpretation of the Vinaya prescription.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Notes: The calendar is arranged in a lunar calendar.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

Notes: all monastic activities such as ordination, repentance, summer retreat are prescribed a specific time in Zichiji.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Planting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Harvest?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Marriage?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Divorce?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Funerary services?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Trade/commerce?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Frequency of festivals?

–Specify: once a year

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

–All members

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

–number: 10

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Pilgrimages?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Feasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: the belief in the afterlife conforms to the typical Buddhist notion of six paths of existence and the possibility of gaining rebirth in another Buddha land

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: in the form of beings in the six paths, or rebirth in another Buddha land.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In human form?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In animal/plant form?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Cremation?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Mummification?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Interment?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Cannibalism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Feeding to animals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Secondary burial?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Many rituals such as the ordination ritual contain parts of inviting Buddhas and bodhisattvas to descend as witnesses.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
– Specify: perfect virtue, wisdom
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can reward

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can punish

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can be hurt?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: make prophet, make monastic rules

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In dreams

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ In trance possession

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Through divination practices

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Only through religious specialists

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Only through monarch

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other form of communication with living

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Buddha, bodhisattva, and local gods are present invited to witness the ritual as if they are present. Buddhist statues and images are required to be treated as if they are Buddha and bodhisattva.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: control weather, hell

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: heavenly beings and local deities might be included

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife belief in Zichiji is combined with Amitabha's Pure Land belief in Yuanzhao's writing. As Pure Land belief was pervasive in Yuanzhao's time, particularly in the final dharma period, Zichiji intentionally emphasizes the importance of seeking rebirth in the Pure Land.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ At specified time in future

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Divine judgment event

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Establishment of new political system

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: none

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Notes: The conventional information is about the specific situation in China and in the Song and the moral aspect is attributed to the original Vinaya texts.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– Only specialized religious class

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE
Region: Northern Song

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there orthopraxy checks?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ By the community?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ By specific individuals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Other?

–Specify: setting boundaries and purification of the ritual space

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: Zichiji contains a detailed prescription on the division of labor in the monastery.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text mention warfare?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

— A Segmentary Lineage

Notes: Nanshan Vinaya school, with a lineage, traced back to Buddha, and Daoxuan as its founder.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: Buddhist communities are expected to receive food as alms from followers. Chapter 38 is on the etiquette of attending social gatherings with laypersons.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Segmentary Lineage

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 26 is about taking care of the sick and terminal care.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The prescription of behavior codes for Buddhist monks and nuns share a great part, but Chapter 29 is written specifically for Buddhist nuns.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Segmentary Lineage

Notes: Nanshan Vinaya school, with a lineage, traced back to Buddha, and Daoxuan as its founder.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Segmentary Lineage

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 26 is about taking care of the sick and terminal care.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The prescription of behavior codes for Buddhist monks and nuns share a great part, but Chapter 29 is written specifically for Buddhist nuns.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: Zichiji contains a detailed prescription on the division of labor in the monastery.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: Buddhist communities are expected to receive food as alms from followers. Chapter 38 is on the etiquette of attending social gatherings with laypersons.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1078 CE - 1271 CE

Region: Northern Song

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